

DJ Codo Nudo: a novel method for seamless transition between songs for electronic music

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Abstract

This thesis presents a novel methodology for selecting, ordering and mixing songs, in an effort to emulate a human DJ. The algorithm presented herewith builds on work done on these individual tasks and combines them. Since the goal of the thesis is to emulate a human performance, a Turing test is used for evaluation, wherein human subjects are asked to distinguish the performance of the algorithm from that of a human being. While the research presented is thorough, it must be understood as a stepping-stone for further work in this area and not the finished product capable of mimicking the art of DJing, which requires years of hard work and dedication to accomplish.

The proposed algorithm entered in the The AlgoRhythms Turing test proposed by the Neukom Institute for Computational Science, in collaboration with the Digital Music and Sonic Arts programs at Dartmouth University and was awarded joint first place.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The music industry has been revolutionised in the last few years with the advent of music streaming services such as Spotify and SoundCloud, and with the evolution of Disc Jockey (DJ) tools such as turntables, controllers and CDJs. DJ performances have taken over venues such as nightclubs and bars from traditional live bands, which need more than one person to perform. Assisted by these tools, modern DJs assess the crowd present in the venue and can mix their own music or tracks from other artists to create the perfect musical ambience suited to a particular venue and crowd.

Recent market trends suggest an increased demand for pre-recorded DJ sessions wherein DJs generate a continuous and uninterrupted stream of music suited for specific environment such as nightclubs, radio stations, bars or dance parties. CITE This trend suggests that users are also interested in DJ sessions for personal listening experience, making full use of the enhancements in home music systems which can recreate the sonic ambience traditionally found in nightclubs. Here, a gap in demand and supply can be observed wherein most of the aforementioned streaming services are focused on giving users a better interface to organize, collect and share their music for personal use but not recreating the work done by a DJ.

This trend was the main inspiration this thesis, which is aimed at emulating a live DJ. The thesis explores the State of the Art MIR techniques, which can be useful to reach an automatic mix of a list of songs. However, to fully emulate a human DJ, we must observe how a DJ performs in a live situation, the kind of feedback that the DJ receives from the audience and the subsequent thought process that allows the DJ to perform. To this end, we explore the different tools used and study the work done by professional DJs. In particular, we pick the brains of a professional techno DJ, Adriana López at Microfusa Barcelona School, in order to understand the tempos and dynamics of the session to be implemented and the mindset of a DJ.

Following this introduction, the thesis is structured as follows; section 2 follows a historical evolution of the definition of the work done by a DJ, section three provides an overview of related state-of-the-art MIR systems, section 4 proposes a methodology for emulating a human DJ and section 5 presents the evaluation results.

2. THE DJ

2.1 Definition, Evolution and Influence

Frank Broughton says on his book *How to DJ Right: The Art and Science of Playing Records* that “DJing is only about mixing other’s albums”. The job of a DJ is only this, and all this, at the same time. In order to clarify the affirmation, which whom can do “A DJ, may produce and mix his own work”; we may modify the phrase as “DJing is only about mixing recordings”. And it is all about that, recordings; everything into music spreading out of live music concerns a recording. The DJ is the person who selects from all that recordings the best parts and presents it compressed to an audience.

The history of DJing starts a few years after the appearance of the first records, the first ever disk-jockey performed in 1903, and was a young guy called Ray Newby who made the first radio music broadcast with a little transmitter in California¹. Some years later, around 1910, radio broadcasting had become usual for the users. In 1910, a French engineer named Leon Gaumont invented the first two turntables system². The Gaumont Chronophone system made possible to play with two vinyls at the same time, making the synchronization between the two songs better and giving the possibility to play songs without interruption.

But the proper term of Disk Jockey appeared in 1943 when Jimmy Savile started playing jazz vinyls in a dance party. Savile was auto-proclaimed the first DJ ever, even still now there are some doubts about that fact. Himself, was the first person who used two turntables to keep the music playing, few years later³. The first considered discotheque was born in Paris in 1947 by Paul Pacine (Brewster, 2014).

Discotheques continued scattering themselves through Europe and United States during the 1950’s and the concept of DJ became popular in Jamaica, where promoters used to perform in dance parties in the streets using huge PA systems called Sound Systems. New equipment specifically designed for DJs was released to the market during the 1960’s, as the first Turntable by Technics⁴, and the first DJ mixer by Rane⁵, which incorporated the crossfade. The companies’ investment on DJ equipment design, made possible to have better control over the mix; in 1969, a DJ named Francis Grasso began using beatmatching to mix songs and keeping the audience dancing without stop⁶.

During the 1970’s and 1980’s the concept of the DJ as an artist, and the creation of new sounds specially conceived for being mixed to take shape. New techniques, as the “break” or “scratching”⁷, were used by Hip-Hop DJs, mostly in the US, to create live sessions. Besides, house music grew up in Chicago as a mix between dance music and electronic sounds. Later, in Detroit, a new style called techno music emerged by removing the disco sounds and keeping only the electronic noise. Techno and house themselves are the base of the electronic music tree as the concept of only electronic music sounds. They were just preceded by other styles as breakbeat, disco or dub, which were usually made by

¹ DJ History: http://iml.jou.ufl.edu/projects/fall09/bein_k/history.html

² Gaumont Chromophone System

<http://www.aqpl43.dsl.pipex.com/MUSEUM/COMMS/auxetophone/auxetoph.htm#gau>

³ Saville Journal Article: <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/culture/music/rockandpopmusic/8857759/Jimmy-Saville-the-big-fixer.html>

⁴ Technics 50th anniversary webpage: <http://www.technics.com/global/50th-anniversary/>

⁵ First crossfade mixer by Rane: <http://www.rane.com/note146.html>

⁶ Francis Grasso interview <http://www.djhistory.com/interviews/francis-grasso>

⁷ DJ History <http://musitronic.blogspot.com.es/2009/01/capitulo-06-historia-de-los-djs.html>

mixing acoustic song music with electronic noises, not electronic music itself. Figure 1 shows a detailed tree of the evolution of the electronic music genres.

Figure 1: Electronic Music Styles tree, retrieved from ⁸

By the 1990's when the acid house music was played, especially in Europe, in events called raves, some artists started to become famous. There were three main scenarios that made it possible: DJs started to become more professional, they were sound engineers, composers and they started producing remixes and selling them. The growth of the remix industry, and especially when Peter Rauhofer won the Grammy to "The best remix of the year 2000" the door of the fame for electronic music composers and DJs was opened. And finally, the special interest by the labels to keep alive the vinyl, avoiding decreasing sells. The way was by selling vinyl recordings of famous DJs remixes, and making DJs spreading them⁹.

In the early decades, electronic music artists, DJs and producers have become very popular in most of the live and recorded music scenarios. DJs are considered as artists and their job is always more technical and creative. Moreover, the concept of the DJ as a "star" is now very common and there are hundreds of famous DJs of dozens of styles performing with very different techniques and styles. The creation and evolution of styles has not stopped, and since the introduction of software (Serato, Traktor...) and new equipment, the job of the DJ is more creative. Most DJs don't even use Turntables, and controllers; effect mixers and software have opened a vast world of choices for each artist.

2.2 Kind of DJs

The DJ plays music sessions in front of an audience (or radio listeners) using musical and visual animation techniques in order to create a better live experience. For that reason, the DJ prepares and organizes the necessary resources for the development of the session.

⁸ Figure 2.1.1 <http://i.imgur.com/wS74mXy.jpg>

⁹ DJ History: <http://musitronic.blogspot.com.es/2009/01/capitulo-06-historia-de-los-djs.html>

Defining styles, ambience and dynamics of the session is one of their main works. The kind of DJ, the place or the audience defines the resulting show¹⁰.

Most of the references talk about three basic kind of DJ's: Radio DJ, Club DJ and Mobile DJ (Broughton & Brewster, 2007; Broughton, Brewster, & Guiu, 2003; Webber, 2007). On the other hand, the classification given at the Microfusa's Professional DJ Course (*Idem*) is, at least, more accurate and more adapted to modern DJ's and breaks with the semantic problem of the other classification. They talk about Resident DJs and Freelance DJs, both explained below.

- **Resident DJ:**

The resident DJ is a professional DJ who performs with regularity in a Club or Radio, and is considered as a permanent employee of it. On that case, there usually exists a specific thematic or target audience and the work of the DJ will be to ensure the manager's requests by creating the proper tracklist and performing as is required. Moreover, this kind of DJ's will participate at the scheduling and spreading of the events (or the radio broadcast) and will be legally responsible for the proper implementation of the occupational risk and ambience risk prevention.

- **Freelance DJ:**

The freelance DJ can perform at Clubs and Radios, but his work is not limited only on this two kind of places; a Freelance DJ usually plays, in addition, at musical bars, concert halls, public musical events, festivals or even at non only musical events as fashion and promo events. The Freelance DJ is considered a freelance worker and is hired for each specific event. He works usually for music production companies and is selected for his artist characteristics, music style he plays or kind of performance he does.

2.3 Kind of Performance

Moreover, exists a second kind of classification, the "DJ Set" and the "Live Act", based on the kind of performance the DJ does. This kind of DJs can be both "Resident" or "Freelance" DJs at work, and even the same DJ can performance with the two techniques on different shows, or mix the two techniques during a show; but there is a clear technical and conceptual difference between them.

- **DJ Set:**

The DJ set is a session made by mixing one song after another using CDJ and/or Turntables and a Mixer. The songs can be complemented with additional samples or Rhythm-Boxes and the DJ can be or not the producer of them. The goal for this kind of performance is usually to mix smoothly the two songs in order to create a continuous ambience and, in some genres, even create an own artistic track within the mix.

- **Live Act:**

The live Act, otherwise, is a session in which one or more artists play a unique and original "on air" or live performance using synthesizers, rhythm boxes and pre-produced and pre-programed sounds with a computer. The technique consists on combine sounds and sequences in order to create an original set, made by songs, or

¹⁰ Professional DJ Course by Microfusa <http://www.microfusa.com/cursos/dj/dj-profesional>

concatenation of sounds and loops. Improvisation is usually used on that kind of performance. This kind of artist needs some skills to create and execute the music and is considered as a musician¹¹.

The first classification is more relevant for our work, as it is very different to record an Acoustic band or a Metal band, the same happens when we try to automate a DJ who play and mix entire songs or another who create a song during the performance by adding and taking out loops, samples or playing melodies with synthesizers. On this work we will analyse the needs for a system to create automatic mixing and, therefore, it will not create original music.

2.4 The Standard DJ Equipment Setup

DJ Equipment:

The basic DJ equipment comprises of a music player (CD or Turntable), a mixer and a microphone. All this hardware get new uses with the arrival of the digital age and, now, all this hardware is used not only as players or mixers, but as midi controllers for DJ software, audio interfaces and even Timecode controllers^{12, 13}. Besides, modern DJs use a large amount of different software controllers and analogue tools for applying internal and external Effects, Samples, loops and a deeper control to the performance.

- **The Turntable:**

The vinyl player is such the first tool used for DJing but, actually, the first turntable specially designed for DJ performance was the “Technics SL1200 MK” (Figure 2). The company was the first to work together with DJs in order to develop a turntable made for DJ technics needs *Ibid.*, p. 3.. The main characteristic of the SL1200 series was the direct-drive system against the belt-drive system. The high torque and reliability of that system were well accepted by DJs and the possibility of performing technics as “Scratching” and having a higher control of the vinyl made direct-drive the standard system for DJ turntable manufacturers¹⁴. Even If more companies are now building DJ turntables, the SL1200 Mk is still a reference model, what means DJ turntables have not suffered large changes in time as other devices.

Figure 2: Technics SL1200 MK DJ turntable

¹¹ Differences between Live Act and DJ set: http://www.electronik.net/web/2011/08/diferencias-entre-un-live-act-y-un-dj-set-por-pitchware-rec/#.VxjPVJOLQ_U

¹² Serato Vinyl Control: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KWDWCZ9qZu0>

¹³ Traktor Timecode Vinyl: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-4pkPIFsvgo>

¹⁴ Technics Direct drive System: <http://www.technics.com/us/introduction/hifi-direct-drive-turntable-system-sl-1200gae/>

- **CDJ (Compact Disk Jockey)**

The main objective of the CDJ is to take advantage of the CD benefits which are: more compact and lasting, and the possibility of creating personalized playlists longer in time than on vinyl. Moreover, it takes the turntable advantages as: vinyl control for beat matching, cues and scratching effects. For that reason, the work between Pioneer and DJs realized with the CDJ-300, the first known CDJ. This kind of widget replaced the turntable in the DJ setup for a while until the appearance of the Timecode control with vinyl, which has made resurface them again. Figure 3 shows different models of CDJ.

Figure 3: CDJ-300, First CDJ model (left) and CDJ-2000NXS, the newest CDJ model (right) of Pioneer

- **Mixer:**

The main characteristic of the DJ mixer is the crossfade. The crossfade allows the DJ changing from a song, playing in one desk, and another song playing in another desk progressively. During the crossfade, the first song's loudness decreases while, at the same time, the entering song's loudness increases, making the transition smooth. Another characteristic is the "Cue" button, which allows the DJ to pre-listen the song before it is sent to the loudspeakers; that allows the DJ to choose a song, change the tempo, and beatmatch with the previous one. Novel DJ mixer models offer the possibility to choose the crossfade curve, and include an infinite number of tools as Equalizers, FX mixer, computer controller, etc. See Figure 4.

Figure 4: Rosie, the first DJ mixer ever (left), and Sixty-four (right) the latest DJ mixer models of the same company, RANE.

2.5 The DJ Equipment Setup

The DJ equipment setup has suffered a large evolution since the first broadcastings with vinyl were made. As the DJ has a more important role into the music performance field, many companies have developed a huge of new tools for better DJ expressiveness. Companies as “Serato”, “Native Instruments”, “Pioneer”, “Technics” in between the most popular have created the most advanced tools to give the control of more variables to the DJ^{15 16 17 18}. The work between DJs and companies reinforces the attribute of musician to the DJ because of the personality and style that DJs can give to their DJ sets, as if they aren’t the producers of the songs.

The basic DJ equipment setup at the beginning was composed by two turntables to ensure the music continuity and a microphone¹⁹, then two channel mixers were included into the setup in order to applying a crossfade between the two tracks, volume, EQ, Fx, and more²⁰. But with the constant increasing of DJ technics and needs, the DJ setup is now a personal choice of the artist. However, there are some different DJ setups used for most of the DJs; some of them influenced for the kind of DJ and the techniques used during the performance. Scratching and beat Juggling, for instance, are techniques which can be performed with CDJ, but where performed on turntables at the beginning with the idea of control the Vinyl twist to generate loops and effects and, many of the DJs practicing this techniques are still using vinyl for having a better feeling during the execution. Figures 5 and 6 present different DJ Setup basic configurations. On Figure 5 we find the early configuration of CDJ and Turntable setups at left and the same configuration as partial or complete DJ Software controller. On figure 6 there is the software-controller-based configurations, even the only computer one. There are many of controllers built for specific software like Serato, Traktor, Ableton..., which are made by the same company of the software or between companies within agreements. All images kept by the

¹⁵ Native Instruments webpage: <https://www.native-instruments.com/en/>

¹⁶ Serato webpage: <https://serato.com/>

¹⁷ Pioneer webpage: <https://www.pioneerdj.com/es-es/>

¹⁸ Technics webpage: <http://www.technics.com/global/>

¹⁹ <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/culture/music/rockandpopmusic/8857759/Jimmy-Savile-the-big-fixer.html>

²⁰ Rane webpage: <http://www.rane.com/>

“TurntableLab” recommended configurations for the most popular setups²¹. Furthermore, DJ equipment setup has infinite possibilities and depends on each artist selection of Hardware and Software. Other instruments as External Effects controllers, Synthesizers, MPCs, or any kind of Midi controller for DJ Software, are usually present on most DJ equipment setups.

To conclude, DJ equipment setup is not deterministic of the kind of DJ, because DJs usually try different equipment setups during their artistic career as Adriana López say on her own words²², but is something closer to the DJ culture, habits and beliefs, and more technical issues as: the kind of life they do, the transport logistics or the stability of the system during the stage. Many DJs have experienced the freeze of the DJ software during the performance with the consequent break of the music session; situations which made some DJs choosing the reliability of DJing automata against DJ software. Other DJs, otherwise, prefer the easiness, compactness and possibilities of Software for their performances.

Figure 5. CDJ (top) and Turntable (bottom) equipment setups, analogic (left) software controller (right)

²¹ Beginners guide to DJ Equipment setups: <http://www.turntablelab.com/pages/beginners-guide-to-DJ-equipment-setups#turntableDJsoftware>

²² Adriana López Resident Advisor web: <https://www.residentadvisor.net/dj/adrianalopez>

Figure 6: Software controller based DJ equipment setups.

2.6 Summary

Different instruments and setups allow Club and Freelance DJs to perform live acts or DJ sets depending on the needs and the artist.

But, what does really do a DJ? Is it possible to make it automatic? Would someone notice the difference between an automatic system for music mixing and a human DJ? And more important, which of the State of The Art tools can make a better job while automating the selecting and mixing process of songs?

At first we need to understand the work of the DJ. On the previous chapter we have seen the difference between a Live Act and a DJ Set, at the current work we will focus on the DJ Sets as the target for our research. Even if the DJ who performs Live acts has to find sounds, loops and songs too, at Live Acts there are more advanced musical skills involved into the process. Otherwise, DJ Sets involve the skills needed in order to control the tools, and it can be creative too; but the mixed songs are pre-produced by others or by the same DJ. What we want to do at the current work is to design a system capable of reproducing the skills of the DJ as selecting pre-produced songs or his skills controlling the DJing tools; what doesn't specifically needs musical theory knowledge.

Furthermore, it is important to notice that the culture of the turntable between the DJs is very extended. In many styles "turntablism" techniques as "breaking beat", "scratching", "looping" or the "punch phrasing" are used in order to generate new sounds and song effects, or even to create new songs by the mixing of loops²³. We will again work into the system discarding these techniques, because DJs playing this techniques, as the DJs who perform Live Acts, are considered as musicians. Our system will, on the other hand, simulate the skills and the creativity for mixing, but not for creating new songs.

At the next section we will review the work of the DJ. That means the process followed by the DJ in order to reach a satisfactory performance.

²³ How to be a DJ tutorial: <http://programa.conoci.es/C%C3%B3mo+ser+un+DJ>

a) The Job of the Artist

- **Previous work:**

Working as a DJ means to select and organize a playlist and present this playlist to the crowd using mixing techniques. The previous work the DJ does at home is to listen a huge amount of music. The DJ moves around finding music, he buys music on the Internet, on markets, vinyl stores... He listens to all this music and select some songs for his playlist, according to his artist style, or the kind of people he prevents there will be at the place. When the DJ arrives to the event place he carries on much more songs that the number of songs which will be played during the event. After selecting these songs, DJs using digital tools usually process the tracks in order to classify them into different folders by BPM, genre, energy, name, harmony... or to find and mark the Onset or some "Hot Cue" points. The same work is done with the vinyl or CDs, by assigning to them "post-its", numbers or putting them into different cases on that case. The objective of this work is to retrieve quickly a song during the event if it seems to be the best option at the moment.

- **Stage work:**

The main goal of a DJ is making people dance. In order to reach that, DJs complement a lights, video, smoke... show with their own performance. The job of the DJ on the stage is to select songs from the at-home pre-selected music during the event, making a suitable playlist for keeping the audience dancing and having fun from the beginning and until the end of the session. Besides, the DJ may make the playlist sounding without stop, as if the whole session was only made by one song. To achieve this, the DJ mixes songs between them, putting one song after the other, but making two or more of them sounding at the same time for some seconds.

The main and more used techniques for mixing on classical and modern DJing are the crossfade and the direct cut, which we will explain better at the next sections. This techniques have the only objective to change from one song to the other, and the only modifications they make to the song is on the Fader and Equalization. Besides, there are hundreds of effects, usually processed by external devices that the DJ can use to make the change from one song to the other smoothly or just richer. A classification of some examples of the most used effects is written below:

- Timber effects: Filters, Wah-Wah, and Pitch Shifters...
- Modulation: Tremolo, Auto-pan, Flanger, Phaser...
- Space simulation: Delay, Reverb, and Echo...
- Others: Distorsion, Gates...

The use of these techniques to mix music depends on the artist and the style he is playing; an EDM DJ would use more effects and a fast mixing because the songs are very rich on melodies and rhythms, so two EDM songs together would probably sound bad. A Techno DJ, otherwise, would use less effects and a longer mix, making the changes as smoothly as possible; that's because Techno songs use to be more lineal and progressive, and most of the songs are written to sound together with other songs without interferences.

Having seen the difference between the homework and stage work the DJ does, we can therefore conclude that, if we need a point to start searching for the best MIR tools to design our system, we could conclude that, a DJ is:

- At home = recommender system
- On Stage = mixing + real time recommender system

We wrote two times the concept of recommender system, and it may seem both are the same. Otherwise, the recommender system at home is very different than on stage. At home the DJ is making an extensive list of music from the same style or maybe useful for the same party. But on stage, the DJ not only have to receive the crowd feedback in order to select the next song, he has to select from a “top hits” list, the best song to play; and this song has to have coherence with the previous one. Usually DJs mix by Beat per minute (BPM) proximity, similarity, compatible harmony²⁴ or even mood. Therefore, the work of “recommending” at stage is directly influenced by the compatibility of the mixing the new song with the previous one. That means not always the best song for the moment will be possible to be mixed or maybe the DJ will have to use more advanced techniques and effects to make the mix possible.

On the next chapter we will review the principal techniques of the state of the art which will make possible to make the process automatically and below we leave brief explanation of why, taking into account the previous chapters. Figure 7 shows a brief schema of the main research on the state of the art techniques and tools, which will be explained on the next chapters.

- **SEGMENTATION:** A DJ segments the song, even if mentally, to know the exact point where to change or introduce the new song, or even put an effect.
- **BEAT TRACKING:** In order to segment and make the beat matching, we need to detect the beats and the Downbeat; that’s the same the DJ does while mixing two songs at time and following the structure of the bars.
- **BEAT MATCHING:** Is the first step a DJ does before start listening the next song he will play with the headphones; the beat of the two songs must match in order to ensure a continuity of the groove.
- **MIXING:** On that section we will view some different mixing effects, at least the most used by DJs. The DJ mixes and he does it by using some these techniques.
- **RECOMMENDATION:** As we said, the DJ is a recommender system, on that point we will focus more on the “On Stage” instead of “at home” recommendation as we explained before.

²⁴ Harmonic Mix: <http://www.hispasonic.com/tutoriales/mezcla-armonica-para-DJs/37594>

Figure 7: schema of the main research on the state of the art techniques and tools, applied to DJ behaviour analysis.

3. Related Work

3.1 Introduction

Music Information Retrieval (MIR) is concerned on the extraction and inference of meaningful features of music, it's indexing and the development of different search and retrieval schemes (Downie, 2003). It started with the analysis of symbolic representations of the songs (mostly MIDI scores). With the evolution of computing systems during the early 2000's, signal processing to extract features directly from the audio, was also included (Manning, Raghavan, & Schütze, 2008). These features are pitch, temporal, harmonic, tumbrel, editorial, textual and bibliographic facets (Downie, 2003).

At the current work we will see some of the MIR techniques used for audio and music segmentation, beat detection, beat matching, mixing and music recommendation.

3.2 Segmentation

Automatic song segmentation is a task of Music Structure Analysis (MSA). On the MIR field, MSA has been studied for the last two decades and it is still widely active at MIREX (“MIREX 2015: Audio Structural Segmentation - MIREX10 Dataset - Introduction,” n.d.). The aim of MSA is to find temporary and structurally meaningful points from a given audio file. The goal is to divide the song into different segments using these reference points, which would mark the change between chorus, verse, intro, interlude, etc. (B McFee & Ellis, 2014). MSA is usually divided into two subtasks: Boundary detection and Structural labelling. For boundary detection task, an exact time for the beginning and for the end of the segment is retrieved. Otherwise, Structural labelling is responsible for grouping the retrieved segments according to their acoustic similarity (*e.g. verse, chorus*). (O Nieto & Bello, 2015). The Structural Labelling process is subordinate to the detection of boundaries and the grouping process is strongly influenced by these boundaries (Serrà, Müller, Grosche, & Arcos, 2014), but even that, some of the existent systems are specialized only in one of the two tasks. On the Table 1 we show some of the current segmentation systems with the tasks they realize. The Table 1 is an adaptation of the table shown at the Music Structure Analysis Framework (MSAF) (O Nieto & Bello, 2015) with some additions. The MSAF is a Framework written by Oriol Nieto and Juan Pablo Nieto with the aim to facilitate the analysis, evaluation, and comparison of algorithms for music structure analysis, on their own words. The algorithm they present can extract the needed features for the latest segmentation systems. It allows the DJ to customize the parameters for feature extraction making the work of comparing and evaluating different systems on the same dataset easily.

Algorithm	Boundary	Structure
2D- Fourier Magnitude Coeffs	No	Yes
Checkerboard Kernel	Yes	No
Constrained Cluster	Yes	Yes
Convex NMF	Yes	Yes
Laplacian Segmentation	Yes	YES
Ordinal LDA	Yes	No
Shift Invariance PLCA	Yes	Yes
Structural Features	Yes	Yes
Neural Networks	Yes	No

Table 1: adaptation of the table shown at the Music Structure Analysis Framework (MSAF) (O Nieto & Bello, 2015)

The features needed for the audio segmentation task are usually related to Tonal descriptors and Spectral descriptors (Bogdanov et al., 2013; O Nieto & Bello, 2015), for that reason Nieto’s MSAF considers Chromagrams, MFCCs, Tonnetz, and Constant-Q Spectrum as standards for the task. Moreover, other descriptors as HPCPs or the mel-scaled logarithmic-magnitude spectrogram (MLS) for the analysis with Neural Networks (Schlüter, Ullrich, & Grill, 2014) can be used. In addition, the segmentation task can be processed with frame, or beat-synchronous features. While the frame-synchronous feature extraction gives more data, on the segmentation task it can add computing costs unnecessarily; assuming that the boundaries for the segments fit with the last beat of the bar; keeping, on that way, the song musicality.

The latest segmentation systems are most of them at the Nieto’s MSAF and we will give a brief description of them, and some more below.

- **2D - Fourier Magnitude Coeffs (2D-FMC)**

The 2D-FMC is a Structure algorithm submitted at MIREX 2014 to the task of structural segmentation. The boundaries are created by using other systems (check Checkerboard Kernel, Convex NMF and Structural Features), generating on that way, three submissions constricted to evaluation. The features used for the task where MFCCs and HPCPs extracted from a one-channel audio file sampled at 44.1Hz using Essentia (Bogdanov et al., 2013). The boundaries were created by using the Multi-Feature Beat Tracking (Zapata & Davies, 2014) implemented in Essentia in order to generate beat-synchronous boundaries. The three characteristics achieved by using the Pitch Class Profiles (PCP) features, and computing the magnitude 2D-Fourier Transform was: key transposition invariance, phase shift invariance, and local tempo invariance. These characteristics, computed from a Chroma representation, are robust and efficient for the labelling of the segments, and by modifying the Maximum, Minimum and Fixed Windows Size for the computation it is possible to estimate the k -means for the segment labelling. For further details on the implementation of the system check (Oriol Nieto & Bello, 2014).

- **Checkerboard Kernel**

The Checkerboard Kernel is a boundary segmentation system which finds significant changes in music or audio. The system is able to find single-note boundaries and natural segment boundaries (eg: chorus, verse, speech/music transitions) by computing local self-similarity. The system computes at each instant the past and the future self-similarity for the frame and the cross-similarity between the past and the future. A boundary is assumed when the self-similarity with the frame is high and the cross-similarity between past and future is low. The audio is parameterized using the magnitude spectrum of the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and the distance matrix is calculated with both the Euclidean distance in parameter space and the cosine angle between the parameter vectors. The distance matrix \mathcal{S} is then correlated with the Kernel. When the regions are similar, using the cosine metric will give values near 1, otherwise, when they are dissimilar, the cosine metric trends to -1. Therefore, to find changes of notes or sections becomes to find inflexion points at the correlation. This task is made by comparing \mathcal{S} with a Kernel radially-symmetric Gaussian matrix similar to a Checkerbox. When the correlation between \mathcal{S} and the Kernel is done, the crux of the Checkerbox shows a change in the structure. For bigger Kernels the changes of natural structure is found, smaller Kernels, otherwise, show changes in notes, beats or bars. For further technical details you can check the original paper found in (Foote, 2000).

- **Constrained Cluster**

The Constrained Cluster method (Levy & Sandler, 2008) is a boundary and structure system based on hierarchical labelling of spectral features. The features for the task are extracted using the AudioSpectrumEnvelope, AudioSpectrumProjection, and SoundModel descriptors of the MPEG-7 multimedia content descriptor standard tool (Casey, 2001). These tools give the necessary descriptors for training a hidden Markov model with a band-divided power spectrum. The system allows being beat-synchronous. The frames of audio or beats are first labelled into one of the k states using the hidden Markov model trained on the features. The results are then used to segment the input sections with a constrained clustering algorithm. The authors conclude that using the constrained clustering is a good approach to get similar human notations in many cases, even when the records are not made with modern recording techniques and, therefore, the irregular forms of the spectrogram are more usual than the *copy-paste* forms of modern recordings.

- **Convex NMF**

The Convex NMF (C-NMF) (Oriol Nieto & Jehan, 2013) is a boundary and structure method from the improvement of the Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) proposed in (Kaiser & Sikora, 2010). The features used for the task are the Chroma Features and the beat and onset detection functions extracted using the Echo Nest API²⁵. The matrixes are then pre-filtered using a median filter, enhanced their Self Similarity Matrix (SSM), and normalized as 0 is very dissimilar and 1 is very similar, in order to get more boundary precision. After that, the decomposition matrix is computed using the (C-NMF). The authors compare the results of the

²⁵ The Echo Nest Analyzer API: <http://developer.echonest.com>

application of the C-NMF and the NMF to the same matrixes and found a very significant improvement of the resolution of the decomposition matrix and to the consistence of the Euclidian distance. The boundaries are found by applying $k = 2$ to the *k-means* clustering, that allows to find local and global structure similarities; Labelling and clustering the segments, otherwise, is done by using the diagonals of the C-NMF to cluster a number of K sections, calculating the Euclidian distance between them.

- **Laplacian Segmentation**

The Laplacian Segmentation (Brian McFee & Ellis, 2014) is a boundary and structure system which uses the Laplacian spectrum to characterize vertex connectivity for song segmentation. The system is very similar to the spectral clustering but with a novel model of representation. The repetition similarity matrix is calculated using constant-Q matrix and the local timbre similarity using the MFCC, all designed in Python with Librosa. The system compares local timbre consistency with long-term repetition descriptors, and gives a compact representation, very effective for finding structure repetition at multiple levels of detail.

- **Ordinal LDA**

The Ordinal LDA is an only boundary system (B McFee & Ellis, 2014). The system makes functional or natural segments for the song (e.g., verse, chorus) integrating the ordinal linear discriminant analysis (OLDA) at the Fisher's LDA (Fisher, 1936) for improving the feature representation of clustering. The authors improve the learning algorithm, furthermore, with a latent structural repetition descriptor, able to facilitate the computation of multiple training examples by generalizing models of repetitions on them. Moreover, the descriptors extracted go from Pitch (median Chroma vectors, and latent Chroma repetitions), Timbre (MFCCs) and Beat descriptors to get beat-synchronous descriptors. The authors noticed that, using the OLDAs increase considerably the boundary detection and computing optimization.

- **Shift Invariance PLCA**

The Shift invariance PLCA is a boundary and structure system based on the shift-invariant probabilistic latent component analysis (SI-PLCA), a probabilistic variant of convoluted non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) (Weiss & Bello, 2011). The algorithm extracts the location of harmonic repetitions among the song in a beat-synchronous Chromagram approach. It divides the song in short patterns and find both the patterns and their repetitions. The aim of the system is to detect motifs, riffs or melodies into the song and minimize the number of parameters specified before. The system, therefore, can found song segments and their boundaries and can be easily used for the segmentation task.

- **Structural Features**

Structural Features (Serra, Müller, & Grosche, 2014) is a boundary and structure system. This system is a combination of structure features with time series similarity. The structure features are the key to cluster the local and global properties of that time series and allow detecting the boundaries between homogeneous, novel and repeated segments. The system is robust to different

parameter settings while detecting equivalent segments corresponding to musical important parts of the song.

- **Neural Networks**

The Neural Networks segmentation system gives boundaries and labels the resulting segments (Schlüter et al., 2014). The algorithm used for the boundary detection is the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), an attempt of labelling the segments is made by a simple model based on 2D-DCTs and a cosine distance measure. The descriptors used to train the Neural Network is a combination of both Mel-scaled log-magnitude spectrograms (MLSs) decomposed with the HPCPs and self-similarity lag matrices (SSLMs), and the SALAMI structural annotation dataset (Grill & Schlüter, 2015). Once the training process is done, the networks are applied to songs. The probability of boundary is computed by the network as a scalar between 0 and 1 for all the spectrogram frames. The analysis of the peaks, windows and thresholds of the resulting curve gives the boundary location. The labelling process is defined as simplistic for the authors and is made by using the 2D-DCTs to create the segments, and hierarchical clustering with a concrete distance threshold to label them.

3.3 Beat and downbeat detection

The analysis of the rhythmic content is a must while designing an intelligent system for audio or music processing. Gouyon and Dixon defines the rhythm as an abstract concept. The rhythm is referred to all the temporal content in a song, whatever its representation is into a score, a performance or into the perception of the listener (Gouyon & Dixon, 2005). Even there is still a lack of consensus at the more philosophical area of the concept of rhythm (Drake, 1993; Drake & Bertrand, 2001), it seems to be agreement that metrical structure, timing and tempo have to be taken in count (Honing, 2001). Either way, the extraction of beat times has become “become” standard for most of the MIR applications, not just rhythmic ones (Zapata, Davies, & Gómez, 2012). This section is dedicated to the description of the most state of the art techniques, descriptors and algorithms for beat detection and finding the downbeat, which will be very useful when designing our automatic auto-mixing system.

a) Beat Detection

- **ESSENTIA BEAT-TRACKER**

The Essentia multi feature beat tracker (Zapata, Davies, et al., 2012) is a beat tracker from Essentia which works as a Framework for one beat tracker algorithm with multiple onset detection input algorithms. The first step to create the system was collect nine onset detection functions from a sort of beat tracking algorithms, for further information of the beat tracker algorithms you can check (Holzapfel, Davies, & Zapata, 2012; Zapata, Holzapfel, Davies, & Oliveira, 2012). The onset functions where: Energy Flux (EF), Spectral Flux (SFX), Spectral Flux Log Filtered (SFLF), Complex Spectral Difference (CSD), Beat Emphasis Function (BEF), Harmonic Feature (HF), Mel Auditory Feature (MAF), Phase Slope Function

(PSF), and Bandwise Accent Signals (BAS). The beat tracker system chosen for the task was the Degara's et al. method described at (Degara, Rúa, & Pena, 2012), it was chosen because its free availability and proved well performance. Degara's system takes an onset detection function, and a periodicity path through time, as an input. The system is a probabilistic framework that integrates musical-knowledge and signal observations to give back the time between consecutive beats and beats location as an output. The system was run with all the onset functions and the results re-grouped into beat tracking sequences committee, using the maximum mutual agreement from the mutual agreement (MA) method described at (Holzapfel et al., 2012; Zapata, Holzapfel, et al., 2012). The evaluation with the large compiled dataset and MIREX evaluation show a significant improvement on beat tracking.

- **LIBROSA BEAT TRACKER**

The Librosa beat tracker (Ellis, 2007) is a simple beat tracker approach based on a dynamic programming method, which estimates a global tempo, and computes the onset strength envelope. Then, due the dynamic programming method, the system finds the onset series with higher onset strength that fits better on the tempo. The tempo estimation in this system minimizes the errors by smoothing and training with a dataset of human tapes for musical clips the onset envelope. The results were evaluated at MIREX-06 achieving results of around 60% accuracy, and detecting changes of tempo changes until around 10%.

- **MADMOM BEAT TRACKER**

The Madmom beat tracking system (Böck, Krebs, & Widmer, 2014) is a multi-model approach to the beat tracking task using multiple neural networks models and levels.

b) Downbeat

- **MADMOM DOWNBEAT PROCESSOR**

The Madmom library offers a Downbeat processor (Böck, Krebs, & Widmer, 2016) which uses Neural Networks to operate directly on the magnitude spectrum, getting from it a classification of the beats and the Downbeats.

3.4 Mixing

The mixing effects and tools are not directly a subject of research themselves, moreover the field of signal processing at the time and frequency domains is concerned to provide the necessary theory to allow engineers to imitate, usually, existing analog effects into the digital. On that section we will afford only the evolution of the Crossfade, which is presented into a Rane company research of the evolution of it (Jeffs, 1999). Letting us to choose between the different Crossfade curves. The rest of effects will be afforded at our system directly from the signal processing.

a) Crossfade

The DJ mixer crossfade was originally designed to ensure smooth transitions between one sound source to another (Jeffs, 1999). The idea of the crossfade is to maintain a constant acoustic energy even there is a change of song. At the beginning the crossfade was done by rotating simultaneously the two faders of the different sources, but it was difficult to accomplish the effect accurately. For that reason a single fader to crossfade between the two sons was invented, suffering among the years, an evolution of the mathematical curve used on it.

Figure 8, from a Rane article of the Evolution of the DJ mixer crossfade (Jeffs, 1999) shows us different kind of crossfade transitions used on their mixer designs; used on different moments and styles of music. The X axis is the travel movement of the fade from left to right and the Y axis the curve model (blue and green) and the energy (red).

Figure 8: “No Dip” Taper for Adding sources (top left), Constant-power response (top right), Medium Taper for Cut In and Pump-it-up (bottom left), Sharp Taper for Cut and Scratch (bottom right)

3.5 Playlist Generation

The playlist generation systems are usually approached from the acoustic audio similarity between songs, from the user preferences or environmental variables study, or the most complex using both of them.

Bashi and Collins (Bashi & Collins, n.d.) use audio similarity descriptors used for tempo and genre stimation and standard similarity as: Standarized moments (mean, variance, kurtosis or skewness), signal descriptors (zero crossing rate, first order autocorrelation, RMS), and spectral descriptors (linear regression, centroid, smoothness, spread, dissymmetry). Another way to create playlists (Crampes, Villerd, Emery, & Ranwez, 2007) approach the problem by applying higher level descriptors (‘rebellious’, ‘cultured’, ‘intelligent’, ‘humoristic’ and ‘rhythmic), extracted from signal and spectral descriptors in order to study DJ expertise, by learning from recorded sessions. Moreover, Flexer and co.

(Flexer, Schnitzer, Gasser, & Widmer, 2008) use audio descriptors for genre classification to create new playlists. Finally, timbral similarity measures, used for most of the DJs (harmonic mix), seem to be consistent while creating new playlists (Steven & Lloyd, 2009).

Besides, the generation of playlists using user environmental data is shown here (Cunningham, Caulder, & Grout, 2008) and (Elliott & Tomlinson, 2006). These authors propose the monitoring of human variables, as skin conductivity, heart rate or the movement controlled by mobile phone accelerometers. Finally, other studies use both, social and acoustic data in order to create new playlists and in addition they use the data from social networks or music streaming services to recommend songs to the users fitting better with their preferences or mood (Bonnin & Jannach, 2014; Chiarandini, Zanoni, & Sarti, 2011)(Chiarandini et al., 2011).

4. METHOD

4.1 Hypothesis

From the beginning of this work we have worked on a research focused on a deeper understanding of the DJ behaviour and we have analysed the closets state of the art MIR techniques which will give us the proper tools to approach a design of our system, with the aim to approximate the DJ behaviour recreation within the use of the computer science.

The main hypothesis of this work arrives from the main motivations and the research done on the field, which we wrote about on chapters one to three. On these chapters we deep analyse the main characteristics of the DJ job and techniques and we view the main MIR state of the art in order to approach the availability of our research. This work made arise the two main research questions of this study:

- Which are the main characteristics for an automatic mixing system to reach the output of a credible automatic session?)
- It is possible to achieve the absolute automatization?

4.2 The Approach

The two main research questions will be our guide to approach the system development during this chapter. The first, and most important concept, is the aim to imitate a human behaviour, the DJ behaviour on that case. A second goal is to design a system assessable, using the correct evaluation methods to test its reliability.

PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH METHODS, TECHNIQUES AND DESIGNS:

The existing methods for psychological research design includes on first instance, and at in any case, the observation of the target behaviour. The method can be quantitative (experimental or semi-experimental) or qualitative (interactive or non-interactive) (Navas, 2001).

We decided to use a qualitative design due to the limitations of a quantitative design on understanding the DJ behaviour. The amount of music styles, DJ techniques, the DJ personality of every artist, and all the environmental variables; make the job of creating a model very difficult. It would have supposed an expensive design with a small vision field and low levels of reliability. For that reason we decided to use a qualitative and interactive design with a case of study. The next section will make a deeper review on how the DJ expertise and the knowledge was recorded, using the DJ course and Adriana López interview.

The technical methodology part was solved by the restrictions of the evaluation model. We presented the algorithm to a contest, which will be explained on the next sections, and which made us choose the best tools for the implementation of the system to fit into the contest rules.

Therefore, the design of the methodology is based on both, technical state of the art MIR techniques and the qualitative psychological research methods in order to fit the psychology of the DJ into the engineering tools for the implementation.

4.3 Professional DJ Knowledge

The main issue to resolve first, if our intention is to emulate the behaviour of a DJ performance, is to know very well how DJs behave. For that reason, the architecture of our design begins by getting closer to DJs, keeping the techniques and the psychology of their behaviour and organizing this information into the theoretical framework of the audio-computing state of the art, from the beginning.

At this point we started collaboration with Microfusa, a Sound engineering, music production and professional DJ school in Barcelona²⁶ in order to learn more about DJs. During the collaboration with Microfusa, we got the opportunity to participate on their *Professional DJ course* given by Adriana López, a techno DJ that we will talk about afterwards. The course is a three-month intensive program that gives all the necessary tools, expertise and practice to become a professional DJ. The course was divided into a theoretical and a practical part. The theory was given and directly putted into practice at the same place and Adriana gave the instructions and tricks to perform as a real DJ at each moment. The content of the course was the listed below:

1. DJ cabin, equipment and configuration
2. Musical Structure and Musical Genres
3. Tempo synchronization
4. DJ set maintenance
5. Equalization
6. Mixing with turntables
7. Mixing with CDJ and digital systems - Rekordbox
8. Mixing with effects
9. Mixing with loops and samples
10. Harmonic Mixing
11. Recording a set
12. Digital playback systems 1: Controllers and audio interfaces: Virtual mix with Rekordbox DJ
13. Digital playback systems 2: Virtual Mixing with Serato DJ
14. Digital playback systems 3: Virtual Mixing with Traktor
15. Digital playback systems 4: Virtual Mixing with timecode CDs and Vinyls.
16. Preparing a DJ set
17. DJ promotion and psychology
18. Professional DJ rooms

As we can see the course content gives not only the techniques to DJ with whatever current tool but all the necessary knowledge to deep understand the DJ job, as knowing the equipment, the gig scenario management or the psychology of the mix. Moreover, we took advantage of Adriana's expertise during the course and got an extended interview with her with the aim to keep subtle knowledge of the art of DJing.

Adriana López^{27 28}: is a Colombian artist based in Barcelona, she is considered to be one of techno's most prominent female artist and true pioneer of Colombia's electronic music scene, as is described at Resident Advisor. She is a techno DJ, international

²⁶ Microfusa Webpage: <http://www.microfusa.com/>

²⁷ Adriana López Soundcloud <https://soundcloud.com/adrianalopez>

²⁸ Adriana López resident advisor web: <https://www.residentadvisor.net/DJ/adrianalopez>

performer, owner of her label “Grey Report”, and a DJ with more than 25 years of experience.

The questions, and a transcription of the key phrases and concepts of the interview are exposed at the Annex 1 and, at next, we will describe the main conclusions about both, the DJ course, and Adriana’s interview, and the use of this knowledge to develop the system with the right assumptions.

- A DJ is someone who loves music and wants to transmit this love to others.
- The DJ drives the party, as a trip.
- You must like the music you mix.
- Don’t listen too much the song, just listen to it fast and organize into *playlists*
- Leave the entire song or practically the entire song
- The change between song don’t have to be noticed, only a few times during the session
- Don’t use too much effects, use them only on changes mostly
- Keep the groove
- Don’t mix songs with a large difference of BPM, don’t change the tempo of the session too fast.
- Most of the songs have the same structure, and follow the rule of having changes each 8 or 16 bars.
- Listen to the audience feedback, they will show you the way

Therefore, we decided to implement a system with the characteristics of these parameters listed above. We designed a system which would simulate a human, but not deterministic. The idea is to create confusion among the audience about the humanity of the system. As every DJ has a style and personality while mixing, and due time and crowd feedback restrictions, was not possible to emulate most of the human DJ behaviours. Therefore we designed the system as if it was humble human DJ. That means, the very professional DJ shows his personality during the session, but don’t need to use too many effects and changes to prove his mettle; so we designed a system which uses different kind of changes, it changes song very smooth, and uses only one or two effects for a session of 15 minutes, leaving the songs being played practically entire. So the result would be a polite session without too much “fireworks”, being modest for the audience, but more human.

4.4. The System

a) Intro AlgoRhythms (inputs)

The Neukom Institute proposed the AlgoRhythms contest for Computational Science, in collaboration with the Digital Music and Sonic Arts programs at Dartmouth. The contest required participants to design an algorithm able to generate a 15-minute session from an electronic dance music (EDM) database. More details about the contest will be shown at the *Evaluation* chapter, where we will deeply talk about the Turing Tests and the evaluation method for the participant systems.

At this section we point the contest rules and restrictions, which made us choose some of the State of the Art methods while implementing the system. The main rules affecting to the system design are the next²⁹:

1. *A contemporary computer should be able to run the code to generate 15-minute electronic dance music sets using less than 32GB of RAM and less than 50GB of disk space.*
2. *Some standard computer music and executable runtime environments may be provided by the Creative Turing Tests team: Java JRE7/8, Python 2.7+, Processing 2.1+, Beads, Max/MSP 6/7, PureData (PD), SC 3.7, Chuck 1.3+.*
3. *Non-system libraries and frameworks must be statically linked, and an executable "RunMe" provided.*
4. *Producing an (effectively) unlimited number of 15-minute WAV files with audibly different musical results. The seed track may be treated either as a random seed (e.g. using its md5 sum) or as a seed track for a playlist algorithm.*
5. *The dance music sets may be generated using one of:*
 - a. *audio-based music information retrieval with a data set of 1000+ commercially distributed EDM tracks from 10 EDM genres: Bass, Drum and Bass, Dub Step, Hard Style, House, Nu Disco, Future House, Techno House, Techno, Trance.*
 - b. *symbolic music generation with self-contained samples, stems, and/or sound synthesis algorithms,*
 - c. *a hybrid of (a) and (b).*
6. *The program must be completely self-contained and require no connectivity to the Internet. Programs must be capable of generating distinct 15-minute dance music sets with high probability.*

These limitations closed us the possibility to use any music processing Api, or libraries as Essentia, which includes dependencies at the computer. Moreover, the possibility to use machine-learning models was discarded because of the computer costs and the possibility to exceed the memory or time restrictions. Therefore, we decided to implement the system using Librosa (B McFee, Raffel, Liang, & Ellis, 2015), which doesn't need dependencies even if we extracted some of the descriptors with Essentia before the Librosa implementations. The effects and changes were designed and implemented manually. A future, and more commercial version would include effects and audio processing tools coming from still developed Apis.

Figure 9 shows the general structure of the system, which we will comment deeply below. The main inputs and outputs are the blue boxes, and the process is the grey box. The inputs are the seed song, the minutes of the session and the number of songs. We leave open to change the minutes of the session and the number of songs in order to test the system with different variables, but not for requirements of the contest. Moreover, the system takes the song from a 1000+ song dataset, makes the selection and mixing process and retrieves, as the output, a session of mixed songs with the length and the number of songs specified.

²⁹ AlgoRhythms Conset Rules: <http://bregman.dartmouth.edu/turingtests/algorithmms>

Figure 9: general structure of the system

b) Recommendation

The recommendation process is shown graphically at the Figure 10 To run the program is given a seed song and the algorithm must generate the set from that song. The contest rules included generating distinct sessions for each run of the program even with the same seed song. So the process to deal with this restrictions and get a satisfactory list was the described below.

We decided to use BPM and Genre descriptors because are standard on music similarity as we wrote at *Related Work* chapter. Moreover, due to contest restrictions, using social or environmental variables for this project was not allowed. For a 15-minute session we decided to not change genre, in order to generate a homogeneous session. Furthermore, differences in tempo between songs of the same style are usually not so large to generate distortion to the song. Moreover, to find 10 target songs of the same style and similar tempo into a 2000 song dataset seemed very feasible. So, the system extracts the genre and BPM for all the 2000 songs, and takes the 10 songs with the nearest BPM and Genre than the seed song. After that, it excludes the seed song from the list and takes 5 random target songs that will be mixed after. We use 5 songs because the target time for most commercial songs is around 3 minutes, as the session was thought for 15 minutes, with 5 songs we ensured to arrive to the 15 minutes of session. And we take 10 songs before in order to generate different sets for each run of the program.

Figure 10: recommendation process

c) Mixing

- **Beatmatching:**

The first process of the system in order to mix the target songs is to make the beatmatching process. The implementation of the beatmatching algorithm is made by generating a *ratio* with the division of the tempo of the song N with the tempo of the first song, and re-writing the rest of the songs using the sampling rate but multiplied with the *ratio*. So the session would follow the tempo of the first chosen song. Moreover, once the rest of the songs are re-written, the beat-tracking process is made again to the songs with the new tempo, and frames in time and the beats and bars are computed again. Figure 11 shows an schema of the beatmatching system. Changes in tempo of less than 10% for a song into a DJ session would not be noticeable for the audience, and we suppose the 10-nearly-in-tempo-to the-seed-song tracks would not pass the 10% of change.

Figure 11: schema of the beatmatching system

- **Direct - Cut:**

The Cut and the Direct-cut are both an effect and a tool. All changes include cutting the song, but effects as crossfade, filtering or drum-roll FX takes more importance than the cut on the change. So we designed a cutting system that is also used at one point of the session as an effect itself, without anything more to change directly from one song to another.

The cutting system cuts the song trying to standardly follow the structure. For a session of 15 minutes and 5 songs, a change of song might be done every 3 minutes of song, but if you cut directly after 3 minutes, the cut will probably not match with the beat and less with the end of the bar, making the change not natural and even less smooth. Therefore, the system cuts the song, once the minute 3 of the song is detected, at the next multiple of 8 bars counted from the beginning of the song. That ensures, in most of the cases, that the cut will match with the end or the beginning of a new natural part of the song. Figure 12, shows the schema of the cutting system, where the arrows are possible points of the minute 3 of the song, and the cut is done at the end of the multiple of 8 bars.

Figure 12: schema of the cutting system

- **Crossfade and Cf Filtered:**

The crossfade FX is considered a standard for mixing, and is the basis of the existence of DJ mixers. After trying with logarithmic and exponential crossfades, we decided to implement a linear crossfade because of the resulting sounding of the mix. Logarithmic crossfade resulted with a noticeable increment of the energy and exponential crossfade a decrease of the energy, so we decided to use the linear crossfade to keep the change smooth. The system multiplies the *magnitude spectrum matrix* frames with a decreasing matrix from 1 to 0 for N frames of the change at the ending song and from 0 to 1 for N frames of the change for the incoming song. During the change there is an overlapping between the two songs for the last and the first multiple of 8 bars of each song. Figure 13 shows the schema of the crossfade system.

Figure 13: schema of the crossfade system

- **Drum Roll FX:**

The Drum Roll FX is an standard effect to generate tension between song changes or song structure changes, on that implementation we noticed the lack of resources to use at the contest. Most of Drum Roll FX processors use in addition reverbs, delays, noise-doors or complex processing. Due the restrictions of time we implemented a basic Drum Roll FX, which cuts the bars progressively for the last 4 bars of the song, before the cut of it, and divides the number of bars for each round, generating a loop. The first loop repeats the last four bars, the second loop repeats the two first of the last for bars (for 4 bars), the third loop repeats the first of the last for bars (for 2 bars), the fourth loop repeats the half of the first bar of the last four bars (for 1 bar), and the last loop repeats the first beat of the first bar of the last four bars (for 1 bar). Figure 14 shows the progression of loops and bars, being at the top the first loop and down the last.

Figure 14: progression of loops and bars, being at the top the first loop and down the last

5. EVALUATION

The evaluation process at this work has been deterministic for the system design; therefore the system was designed using the knowledge extracted from the research but with the restrictions of the externally proposed evaluation. We took advantage of the AlgoRhythms contest in order to evaluate the system with final users, compare it with the performance of other systems and having an structured and reliable evaluation.

The evaluation process was done into the AlgoRhythms contest, proposed by the Neukom Institute for Computational Science, in collaboration with the Digital Music and Sonic Arts programs at Dartmouth College (USA). The contest was part of a group of Turing Tests in Creativity that tested the “humanness” of algorithm-generated poems, short stories and DJ sets. The results and a part of the evaluation were carried at the 2016 Digital Arts EXposition (DAX) at Dartmouth on May 2016³⁰.

a) Turing Tests

The Turing Test was proposed by the computer scientist a Alan Turing (Turing, 1950). The experiment was designed with the aim to evaluate and determine machine intelligence. On a Turing Test, the experimental variables are hidden from the participants; the variables A and B (figure 5.1) are a computer running a program (A) or a human (B). The computer is designed to retrieve analogue answers, similar to the human ones. The participant interacts with both A and B during the experiment, and when it finishes he has to determine the condition of A and B as human or machine. On that case, if the participant classifies A as a human, the algorithm passes the Turing Test, being accepted as intelligent. Figure 14 shows a representation of a Turing Test experiment.

Figure 14: Representation of a Turing Test experiment

³⁰ Dartmouth Turing Tests webpage: <http://bregman.dartmouth.edu/turingtests/>

b) AlgoRhythms

The AlgoRhythms contest is a Turing Test designed to determine if a machine-based DJ session could be considered as made by a human. Therefore, DJ sessions of 15 minutes were computed by the participant algorithms and after presented to the experiment participants, mixed with human-recorded DJ sessions, in two evaluation phases:

1. **On-line poll:** 16+ DJ sessions, half human sessions, half algorithmic sessions, were presented online. People were called to vote if human or algorithm made each session. We don't know the exact number of people on that part of the evaluation because deeper details of the research were asked to the experimenters and are not still available. But, considering the current votes for the post-experiment on-line poll, still available at the AlgoRhythms webpage, the number of participants was around 300 people.
2. **Dance Party:** It was organized a Dance Party, on May 18th, 2016, during the Digital Arts EXposition (DAX) at Dartmouth³¹. During the party, the first three scored algorithms at the on-line poll were chosen to present another 15 minutes session, in combination with three human DJ, all back to a black mirror. There were over 350 participants during the event, which were invited to vote each set via SMS/web, choosing the set as made by a human or an algorithm.

The algorithm submission of the system is available online in an open source implementation, you can find it at

https://github.com/JaumP/JaumePritish_AlgoRhythms_DJ_Cojo_Nudo

The design of the system was completely done by the author; Pritish Chandna did the algorithm architecture design, and it was programmed and submitted together to the AlgoRhythms contest.

³¹ Digital Arts EXposition (DAX) webpage: <http://www.dax.cs.dartmouth.edu/>

6. RESULTS

Detailed results for the first round of evaluation are not still available, but we know there was one entry (the second score at the second round) which achieved ~50% Human / ~50% Machine, our system achieved at this round ~45% Human / ~55% Machine, the rest were not close to our results. Five of the eight submitted entries didn't pass to the second round of evaluation, being discarded after the on-line evaluation.

The vote distribution for Human versus Algorithm for a novel output generated by our program at the second round of evaluation (the Dance Party), DJ Codo Nudo, was 39% Human / 59% machine. There was one other entry (of 8 working submitted entries) that achieved a similar result to our (38% Human / 59% machine) another entry got 28% Human 68% machine, and none of the others were close, further details of the other systems are still not available. On words of Michael Casey³² “*Whilst it did not technically achieve the greater than 50% Human vote that we had set to "pass the Turing test", the fact that 40% of the audience voted for Human is a significant achievement.*”

Being the results tied comparing the first and the second round of evaluation for the first two systems, our system, DJ Codo Nudo and CJ Carr and Zack Zukowski (Medford, MA, USA) were awarded to share the first prize of 2000\$ of the contest.

³² Michael Casey Dartmouth University profile: <http://bregman.dartmouth.edu/~mcasey>

7. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The thesis proposes an algorithm, which, within certain constraints, is able to replicate to a certain degree the performance of a DJ in a live setting, without taking into account audience feedback.

However, as observed in the research presented in the thesis, to truly emulate a DJ, quantification and categorization of this feedback is highly important. To further this research, we propose deep-diving into the nuances of live DJ performances at live venues.

Also, while this thesis provides a generalised case study of the work done by a DJ, the personal touch that is provided by each specific DJ can be studied by analysing the DJs of different genres. To this end, we suggest building an annotated database of pre-mixed DJ performances, specifically studying the transitions between songs.

Finally, we have used a specific music library, Librosa, for analysis, but suggest evaluation of the system using other music libraries such as EchoNest and Essentia.

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